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*Global Climate Change
Amplifies Aquatic Invasive
Species Impacts*

PROGRAM AND ABSTRACTS

Netherlands Food and Consumer
Product Safety Authority
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RESEARCH INSTITUTE
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Invasive
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Marine alien invasive species: assessing the cost of degradation of marine ecosystems in France

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In accordance with the marine strategic framework directive (MSFD) in the EU (2008), we propose in this work an assessment of the cost of marine degradation imposed by invasive alien species in France. The aim of this work is first to present and evaluate the different possible impacts of non-native invasive species within the methodological framework adopted by the group of experts on the "costs associated with the degradation of the marine environment". The degradation of the marine environment caused by invasive alien species is considered in relation to the perceptible damage. The measures implemented to deal with the presence of non-native invasive species include monitoring and information measures, prevention measures and measures to mitigate the impacts observed. The analysis is completed by a characterization of the residual impacts, impacts that persist despite the measures taken to control invasive alien species. Then the various impacts are analyzed. Finally, a discussion of the first results of the current assessment and the two previous MSFD cycles is provided.

Marine invasive alien species (IAS) of Sri Lanka: are we looking at the tip of the iceberg?

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Ports have long been considered as the main entry points of marine bio-invasions as they facilitate the introduction of non-indigenous species (NIS) via shipping activities. Once established such NIS could act as invasive alien species (IAS), competing with native biota for food and space. Financial and ecosystem damages caused by such marine IAS are well evident from available literature and seemingly increasing with the ever-escalating marine traffic. Even though studies on biofouling communities are limited in Sri Lanka, various globally invasive macro-fouling organisms have been recorded. These include the American cupped oyster (*Crassostrea virginica*), the Pacific oyster (*Magallana gigas*), the European flat oyster (*Ostrea edulis*), the Hooded oyster (*Saccostrea cucullata*), the Asian date mussel (*Arcuatula senhousia*), the Mediterranean mussel (*Mytilus edulis galloprovincialis*), the Common periwinkle (*Littorina littorea*), the Australian acorn barnacle (*Austrominius modestus*), the Striped barnacle (*Amphibalanus amphitrite*), the Goose neck barnacle (*Lepas anatifera*), Killer algae (*Caulerpa taxifolia*), and the European shore crab (*Carcinus maenas*). Lack of baseline data, genetic confirmations and periodic monitoring has limited possibilities of determining the invasiveness of these aliens however. Moreover, cryptic fouling organisms may have been overlooked, as was evident in a recent study recording the invasive bryozoans *Watersipora subtorquata* (red-rust bryozoan) and *Schizoporella errata* (branching bryozoan) for the first time in the Port of Colombo. To get a better understanding of the impact of marine NIS in Sri Lanka, a fouling community study is organized during which settlement plates will be deployed in the waters adjacent to the Port of Colombo. Identifications of the organisms on the fouling plates will be based on their morphology in combination with DNA-analyses. This study will focus specifically on colonial ascidians, as these species have not been studied yet in the region and may therefore include cryptic alien species that were overlooked in the past.